

A Plug-in Approach to Controlled Vocabulary Support in Dataverse

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Abstract

Rich metadata is important for data discovery and reuse. Further, the use of standardized values - from community-developed vocabularies and from identifier services for people, organization, grants, and other real-world entities - can further improve human and machine understanding of the data. However, building support for the broad range of existing vocabularies directly into repository software can take significant initial and ongoing effort and potentially limit the flexibility to adopt new vocabularies over time. In the open source Dataverse software project, we've explored a light-weight, plug-in approach to adding this functionality. With this design, the logic related to specific vocabularies and services is isolated in components that know nothing about Dataverse's internals which opens the door to their reuse in other repositories and to shared maintenance. This paper introduces the design and discusses working examples that integrate with external identifier and vocabulary services.

Keywords: FAIR, Semantic, Discoverability, Sustainability

Introduction

Controlled vocabularies (CV) are community defined constructs that identify a limited set of defined values and, in most cases, associate metadata, such as a human-readable short name and definition with a globally unique identifier. Similarly persistent identifier (PID) systems provide both a globally unique identifier, provenance information, and metadata about entities of a certain type, e.g. people, organizations, or grants. Using CVs and PIDs in a repository can improve FAIRness and can also eliminate the need for the repository to manage the metadata about CV terms and PIDs since that work is done by external communities and/or via online services. Web-accessible services are almost always available for PID systems (due to the constant change as new PIDs are registered) and may be available for CVs, e.g. through services such as Skosmos. From a repository perspective, services eliminate even the need to store the set of available CV values as they are always available on demand.

Despite the recognized value in using CVs and PIDs in repositories, their inclusion is still relatively rare. There are many reasons for this, many predicated on an assumption that relatively tight coupling between the repository and the CV/PIDs is required to have a satisfactory user experience:

- CV/PID systems are implemented in a variety of languages including XML, JSON, and RDF and have their own programming interfaces,
- CV/PID systems may or may not support internationalization/be available in required languages,
- CV/PID systems, especially ontologies and taxonomies, can be large (e.g. millions of entries) and may have internal structure, e.g. a hierarchy, necessitating sophisticated selection/search strategies,,
- CV/PIDs can include a wide range of metadata that could/should be included in the display,
- CV/PIDs may not cover the full range needed in a general purpose repository. Repositories may then want to allow use of multiple vocabularies/PID types and/or make their use optional, i.e. allowing free text entries as well, e.g. for metadata such as “keywords”,
- Developers need to understand the CV/PID system structure and API in order to integrate it into the repository, and
- Development and ongoing, long-term maintenance of any integration falls to repository staff.
- Many users are not familiar with the use of controlled vocabularies and user interfaces may need to provide significant guidance.

Somewhat lost in this characterization of the integration challenge is that, at the most basic level, supporting CV/PIDs in a repository means being able to store and retrieve the simple global identifiers for terms - usually strings or URLs. This is something all repositories already do since they allow user input of metadata in the form of strings or URLs already. In our work on Dataverse, we've asked how much can we limit the changes in a repository's codebase to just this and conversely, how much can we make code for input and display of CV/PIDs independent of the details of the repository. As reported here, while there are limits on how complete this separation can be, it is possible to design generic CV/PID support into a repository's base code and to limit the development required for a specific CV/PID to a plug-in, one that can potentially be shared across different repository implementations.

Background

Dataverse is an open-source data repository application originally developed at Harvard University and now also supported by a wide range of community contributors. There are over 90 production Dataverse instances world-wide, many of which provide services to additional institutions. Harvard's Dataverse instance, for example, is open to researchers world-wide, and the DataverseNL (Netherlands) and DataverseNO (Norway) instances provide services to more than 15 institutions in their countries. Dataverse provides a wide range of functionality from basic support for users to upload data, add metadata, keep provenance information, publish datasets with a DOI or other identifier to support for previewing and analyzing data files, allowing anonymization for review, and standards-based long-term archiving. Most relevant to the current topic, Dataverse provides a mechanism for administrators to add new metadata fields and create completely new metadata schema, to organize fields, e.g. for an author field to

have name and email subfields, to associate fields with community schema such as <https://schema.org>, and to display and export metadata in a variety of standards-based formats.

Dataverse has long had support for indicating that a field has a list of controlled values and to specify those values internally, with labels that can be translated to desired languages. This works well for smaller, relatively static CVs where Dataverse's basic capability to provide a drop-down list of choices is sufficient. Internally, Dataverse just stores a database identifier for a chosen CV value. Code to find the associated label, in the required language, is invoked in four places - for input, display of dataset metadata, search queries and results, and various exported metadata formats.

Design

As requests for support for larger, more complex CVs and for the use of PIDs for real-world objects came in from the community, the Global Dataverse Community Consortium initiated an effort to characterize the new requirements and develop an appropriate design(s). Two use cases helped to focus the effort:

CVs published using Skosmos service. Skosmos is a general controlled vocabulary service providing a REST-style API and Linked Data access to the underlying vocabulary data that can be used with any vocabulary representable using the Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS). Skosmos provides an API for doing partial searches (i.e. finding all terms that match what a user has typed so far), and for retrieving metadata about a term including human-readable labels in available languages, short definitions, etc. Skosmos, originally developed and maintained in Finland, was seen as a good representative of CV services in general, was in use by Dataverse community members in Europe and beyond, and had the additional benefit of supporting a case where one field, e.g. keywords, might accept values from multiple vocabularies. From a technology point of view, Skosmos is a frontend connected to Jena Fusek (a triple store with SPARQL endpoint) integrated with SOLR/Elasticsearch search engine. Skosmos allows uploading and using any controlled vocabulary represented in SKOS.

PIDs for people provided via the ORCID registry. By design, PID registries are constantly adding new values. ORCID raises additional issues: peoples names are not unique and hence additional metadata (e.g. email, affiliation, educational history) is required to find the PID for a specific individual and can also be useful when displaying an entry, and not everyone uses ORCID, hence free-text entries are still needed to provide a general mechanism for listing authors, adding contacts, etc. Like Skosmos, ORCID has a public API that can be used to search for a given individual and to return metadata about a given identifier.

Based in part on work in earlier systems to provide Javascript lookup of ORCID identifier to display a name (e.g. the SEAD repository), on the example in Dataverse where JSON-formatted configuration information is used to associate HTML and JavaScript file previewers with

Dataverse, and with a general desire to minimize coupling between Dataverse and external services, the community began to implement a mechanism for CV and PID support involving three main elements:

- A JSON-based configuration mechanism associating specific Dataverse metadata fields with a Javascript, service endpoint, required vocabulary(ies) and other relevant metadata.
- Annotation of all HTML input and display elements used for those fields with custom data-* attributes as defined in the HTML specification.
- Service specific JavaScripts that find repository metadata fields for input and display via the data-* attributes, generate custom HTML elements for service/vocabulary specific input and display, and interact with the underlying services to find/display the values of interest to users.

The initial work was done in the European SSHOC project (Skosmos) and by the Qualitative Data Repository (ORCID). Community design discussions were held and a common design with additional flexibility was finalized with support from the Global Dataverse Community Consortium.

As work proceeded, two additional elements were added:

- Additions to the original elements to allow a script to add metadata about a CV value/PID to other fields, i.e. for the vocabulary name and identifier to be added to other child fields or for a person's name or email to be added in addition to their ORCID.
- Addition of a configuration option and back-end caching mechanism to allow Dataverse to store metadata about a CV value or PID for future use in generating metadata exports (which is done on the back-end where the JavaScripts used in the UI are not available).

The initial release of these capabilities was added to Dataverse v5.7 in October 2021. To demonstrate the new capabilities, we also created a custom metadata block for Dataverse, Javascripts for Skosmos and ORCID services, a JSON Schema for the configuration file and an example file managing three fields: one ORCID field and two with Skosmos - one allowing two vocabularies and one relying on the Javascript to fill in multiple child fields. The following figures show various aspects of the display, configuration, and underlying mechanism involved.

The screenshot shows a web interface titled "External Vocab Support Demo". It contains several sections with input fields and buttons:

- Compound Skosmos Keyword Demo:**
 - Vocabulary: unesco
 - Vocabulary URL: http://skos.um.es/unescothes/CS000
 - Term: Precious metals
 - Term URL: http://skos.um.es/unescothes/C03108
- Creator Demo:**
 - Input: https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8462-650X
 - Search prompt: Find by name, email, or ORCID
- Skosmos Demo:**
 - Input 1: http://skos.um.es/unescothes/C03107
 - Input 2: http://aims.fao.org/aims/agrovoc/c_6161

Each section has a "+" and "-" button to the right of the input fields.

Figure 1: The Dataverse ‘Edit Metadata’ interface for the example fields without external vocabulary support. The first field is compound and provides four text inputs where the user can specify the name and URL of the vocabulary used and of the term within the vocabulary. As all fields are plain text, Dataverse does not check that entries in the child fields are consistent. The second and third fields are single text inputs where users can add an ORCID identifier or Skosmos term. Again, Dataverse does not validate or constrain the inputs.

The screenshot shows the "Creator Demo" field with a dropdown menu open. The dropdown list contains the following entries:

- James Myers, 0000-0001-8462-650X, jim.myers@computer.org
- Myers NCSA
- Myers NCSA
- James Myers, 0000-0001-8462-650X, jim.myers@computer.org
- Seid Koric, 0000-0002-7330-6401
- Sharon Glotzer, 0000-0002-7197-0085
- Alberto Bernal Escribano, 0000-0002-8931-6989
- Makennah Mills, 0000-0001-9198-484X

The first entry is highlighted in blue. There are "+" buttons to the right of the input field and the dropdown list.

Figure 2: Input via the ORCID JavaScript. The script hides the original input field and replaces it with a dynamic list populated by a query to ORCID’s API for entries matching the text typed by the user. In this instance, a last name and previous place of employment are sufficient to identify the author. The display shows the name, ORCID, and email (if public) of the selection. Free text is also allowed in the example configuration - users can select the top entry to store exactly what they typed which handles cases where a person does not have an ORCID. To show the potential for more sophisticated scripts, the ORCID JavaScript uses local browser storage to track previous selections and to shift them to the top of the list. When a user makes a selection, the ORCID identifier or free text input is stored in the hidden Dataverse input field. Dataverse saves this entry exactly the same way it would have if the user had typed it in directly.

Figure 3: Input via the Skomos JavaScript. As with ORCID, the original input field is hidden. In this case, it is replaced by both a vocabulary selector and a dynamic term selection list.

Figure 4: Selecting an alternate vocabulary hosted on a Skosmos server.

Figure 5: Selecting a term from the chosen vocabulary. As with the ORCID JavaScript, the Skosmos script dynamically populates the list with terms matching what the user has typed.

Figure 6: Input via Skosmos for a compound field. While the user still selects only the term from the dynamic list, the Skosmos script has hidden all four child fields and, upon selection, fills out all of them (as shown in Figure 1) and all are saved by Dataverse.

External Vocab Support Demo ^	
Compound Skosmos Keyword Demo	unesco http://skos.um.es/unescothes/CS000 Precious metals http://skos.um.es/unescothes/C03108
Creator Demo	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8462-650X
Skosmos Demo	http://skos.um.es/unescothes/C03107 ; http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_6161

Figure 7: Display without external vocabulary support. Dataverse displays exactly what was entered - the term/PID URLs, or, for the first compound field, the names/URLs of the vocabulary and the term.

External Vocab Support Demo ^	
Compound Skosmos Keyword Demo	Precious metals
Creator Demo	Myers, James
Skosmos Demo	Precambrian; precipitation

Figure 8: Display with external vocabulary support. The ORCID and Skosmos JavaScripts read the original entries and replace them with a more human-readable form - the term name in the user's language configured as a link to the terms webpage. For ORCID, in addition to the link to the person's ORCID profile, hovering over the link shows their email (if publicly available from ORCID).

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dataverses (2)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Datasets (6)
<input type="checkbox"/> Files (8)
Dataverse Category
Department (2)
Publication Year
2022 (5)
Publication Status
Published (4)
Draft (3)
Unpublished (3)
Author Name
Admin, Dataverse (5)
Myers, Jim (1)
Subject
Computer and Information Science (4)
Earth and Environmental Sciences (1)
Mathematical Sciences (1)
Social Sciences (1)
Deposit Date
2022 (6)
Skosmos Demo
Precambrian (2)
precipitation (1)

Figure 9 (left): One of the demo fields promoted as a search facet on the Dataverse collection page (bottom of the list). Once again, the JavaScript replaces the URLs with a human readable form. Other search query and result display fields work similarly - the JavaScripts replace the URI with the term name in the user's language.

```
<input id="datasetForm:tabView:j_idt1613:1:j_idt1616:2:fieldvaluelist:1:cvocInputText"
name="datasetForm:tabView:j_idt1613:1:j_idt1616:2:fieldvaluelist:1:cvocInputText"
type="text" value="http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_6161" class="ui-inputfield ui-
inputtext ui-widget ui-state-default ui-corner-all form-control ui-state-filled" data-
cvoc-parent="skosterm" data-cvoc-managedfields="" data-cvoc-vocabs="
{&quot;unesco&quot;;
{&quot;vocabularyUri&quot;;&quot;http://skos.um.es/unescothes/CS000&quot;;&quot;uriSpa
ce&quot;;&quot;http://skos.um.es/unescothes/&quot;};&quot;agrovoc&quot;;
{&quot;vocabularyUri&quot;;&quot;http://aims.fao.org/aim
s.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/
&quot;}}" data-cvoc-filter="" data-cvoc-service-url="https://skosmos.dev.finto.fi/"
data-cvoc-protocol="skosmos" data-cvoc-allowfreetext="true" lang="en" aria-
label="Additional Entry" role="textbox" aria-readonly="false" aria-disabled="false"
wtx-context="E1612EF8-35A8-4BA6-A10C-351E6575A332">
```

Figure 10 (above): To enable JavaScripts to find the fields they should manage, Dataverse annotates them with appropriate data-* attributes. The HTML source for the input example above includes attributes that specify "skosmos" as the protocol, and indicate which Skosmos server should be called and which vocabularies to allow, to allow free-text entries, and to display terms in English.

```
<span data-cvoc-service-url="https://skosmos.dev.finto.fi/"
data-cvoc-protocol="skosmos" lang="en">
http://skos.um.es/unescothes/C03107</span>
```

Figure 11: The HTML source for a display field. As in the input example, data-* attributes indicate which script should be invoked (skosmos), which Skosmos server should be used for the lookup, and which language should be used for translation. The term URI itself is the text value of the HTML element.

```
{
  "field-name": "compoundDemo",
  "term-uri-field": "compoundDemoTermURI",
  "cvoc-uri": "https://skosmos.dev.finto.fi/",
  "js-url": "https://gdcc.github.io/dataverse-external-vocab-support/scripts/skosmos.js",
  "protocol": "skosmos",
  "retrieval-uri": "https://skosmos.dev.finto.fi/rest/v1/data?uri={0}",
  "term-parent-uri": "",
  "allow-free-text": false,
  "languages": "en, fr, es, ru",
  "vocabs": {
    "unesco": {
      "vocabularyUri": "http://skos.um.es/unescothes/CS000",
      "uriSpace": "http://skos.um.es/unescothes/"
    }
  },
  "managed-fields": {
    "vocabularyName": "compoundDemoVocabulary",
    "termName": "compoundDemoTerm",
    "vocabularyUri": "compoundDemoVocabularyURI"
  },
  "retrieval-filtering": {
    "@context": {
      "termName": "https://schema.org/name",
      "vocabularyName": "https://dataverse.org/schema/vocabularyName",
      "vocabularyUri": "https://dataverse.org/schema/vocabularyUri",
      "lang": "@language",
      "value": "@value"
    },
    "@id": {
      "pattern": "{0}",
      "params": ["@id"]
    },
    "termName": {
      "pattern": "{0}",
      "params": ["/graph/uri=@id/prefLabel"]
    },
    "vocabularyName": {
      "pattern": "{0}",
      "params": ["/graph/type=skos:ConceptScheme/prefLabel"]
    },
    "vocabularyUri": {
      "pattern": "{0}",
      "params": ["/graph/type=skos:ConceptScheme/uri"]
    }
  }
},
}
```

entries allow Dataverse to retrieve the specific elements desired from the remote service’s response (which may include information that Dataverse does not need). The configuration file is sent to Dataverse via its standard Settings API as the :CVocConf setting.

Figure 13 (right): The cached information for the Skosmos Unesco Thesaurus entry for “Precambrian”. The entry includes the vocabulary URL and the term and vocabulary names translated to the languages - all as defined in the configuration (Figure 12).

An excerpt from the OAI-ORE metadata export for the example field storing an ORCID identifier. The cached information from the ORCID service allows Dataverse to expand the entry to include the personName and scheme, and to add the @type Person.

Figure 12(left): The JSON configuration used by Dataverse to associate the Skosmos JavaScript with the compound example field. In addition to information that is copied to data-* attributes as discussed above, the configuration includes a link to the desired JavaScript so Dataverse can load it, the name of the metadata field that will be managed by the script. The retrieval-url and retrieval-filtering entries tell Dataverse how to retrieve JSON/JSON-LD information about the term which is then cached for later use. The “pattern” and “params”

```
"extVocabDemoMetadata:skosterm": [
  {
    "@id": "http://skos.um.es/unescothes/C03107",
    "termName": [
      {
        "lang": "ru",
        "value": "Докембрий"
      },
      {
        "lang": "fr",
        "value": "Précambrien"
      },
      {
        "lang": "en",
        "value": "Precambrian"
      },
      {
        "lang": "es",
        "value": "Precámbrico"
      }
    ],
    "vocabularyName": [
      {
        "lang": "ru",
        "value": "Тезаурус ЮНЕСКО"
      },
      {
        "lang": "fr",
        "value": "Thésaurus de l'UNESCO"
      },
      {
        "lang": "es",
        "value": "Tesauro de la UNESCO"
      },
      {
        "lang": "en",
        "value": "UNESCO Thesaurus"
      }
    ],
    "vocabularyUri": "http://skos.um.es/unescothes/CS000"
  }
],
}
```

Figure 14 (right): The entry for the ORCID example field in the Dataverse OAI-ORE metadata export. The cached information from ORCID allows Dataverse to add the “personName” and “scheme” and to add the “@type” Person.

```
"creator": {  
  "personName": "Myers, James",  
  "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8462-650X",  
  "scheme": "ORCID",  
  "@type": "https://schema.org/Person"  
},
```

Discussion

The figures and captions above provide details on how a relatively simple change in Dataverse - annotating input and display elements with a few data-* attributes - allows use of external JavaScripts to provide external controlled vocabulary and PID support. The required data-* attributes are vocabulary and service independent while the JavaScripts themselves know nothing about Dataverse - they simply respond to the inclusion of the data-* attributes. The addition of a configuration mechanism allows the addition of new JavaScripts over time and allows them to be applied to any new metadata fields that may be added. That said, a simpler repository with a fixed set of input fields could add the same data-* attributes and leverage the same JavaScripts without any changes to support input and display of CVs and PIDs. (CSS Styling could then be used to match the dynamically generated HTML to the local style of the repository.) Similarly, while we did add custom code to Dataverse to support caching and inclusion of human-readable metadata about the selected term/PID in metadata exports, this is optional in the sense that including just the term/PID URI itself preserves machine readability. Further, if caching is desired, our design still keeps the specifics for a given CV/PID system in the configuration document and the code itself is vocabulary/PID independent, reducing implementation cost.

We believe the design as-is is well suited to a range of CV/PID systems, specifically those for which existing services can provide an API for searching for a given term and for retrieving metadata for that term and that use a URI/URL for the term/PID. This would be the case for PID providers such as FundRef (funding sources), ROR (research organizations), IGSN (physical samples), and DOIs (e.g. papers related to datasets), and for any vocabularies that can be published via Skosmos or that have their own access services meeting the outlined requirements.

Our examples have focused primarily on searching for a term via lookup in a dynamically generated list but the mechanism itself is not limited to this and JavaScripts could be written to provide interfaces more appropriate to a given vocabulary/PID. For example, for large, hierarchical vocabularies, navigating down the tree of options may be more natural. Or, for a geospatial gazetteer, allowing selection from and display on a map might be more appropriate. For Skosmos, which supports the SKOS notions of broader, narrower and related terms, an interface allowing navigation over these relationships could be developed.

While more sophisticated interfaces may have higher development costs and require more maintenance, we hope that our design offers an opportunity for such costs to be shared - across repositories and/or with third parties and the groups developing CV/PID systems and the

services to provide APIs to them. Further, once any JavaScript is created for a given CV/PID system, since the code is repository-independent, any adopter could provide enhancements that would benefit all whenever development resources become available.

We do see limitations to the design we've implemented and, while it should support many CV/PID systems beyond ORCID and Skosmos, further work may be needed to support other classes of vocabularies and/or more complex metadata structures. For example, vocabularies defined in XML do not have an obvious URI form for terms and it may be necessary to use some form of hierarchical path based identification to be able to store a term in one text field. Alternatively, it may be possible to write JavaScripts that split such a path across multiple metadata fields stored by the repository. We have identified use cases where look-up services simply don't create a globally unique identifier for an entry, e.g. an internal employee registry, or a gazetteer that maps a place name to a bounding box. There are also cases where term metadata may or may not be desired, i.e. when ORCID lookup is used to find an author, their affiliation(s) in ORCID may or may not be the one appropriate for a given dataset. Currently the only mechanism to handle these in Dataverse is a more general mechanism to include custom JavaScripts. This mechanism does not currently take advantage of the configuration mechanism, data-* attributes, or caching of our external vocabulary support mechanism which makes it harder to see how they could be shared across repositories. We are hopeful that at some point the two mechanisms can be integrated and that it will be possible to handle the broader set of use cases with reusable plug-ins as well.

Conclusion

Despite the acknowledgement that CV/PIDs are important for data discovery and reuse, and despite the work to define and make them available, the fact remains that their adoption in data repository software is relatively low. As argued here, we believe that this is exacerbated by an assumption that implementation would involve tight coupling between a repository and CV/PID services which impacts the breadth of knowledge required and costs. In the Dataverse community, we have designed and implemented a lightweight, loosely coupled design that provides a generic mechanism for using external CV/PIDs in a repository and limits the CV/PID-system-specific code to reusable JavaScript plug-ins. In Dataverse, we expect to use this mechanism to support integration with people, organization, and funding registries as well as with domain specific CV/PIDs to support the broad range of Dataverse users. We also expect to make these plug-ins available under an open-source license and to work with other repository developers and VC/PID providers to increase their adoption and support their long-term sustainability.

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